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The theme of Death, Insignificance and Absurdity in Tom Stoppard's Play, *Rosencrantz and Guildenstern are Dead*

Rakesh Patel*

Rosencrantz and Guildenstern Are Dead is Tom Stoppard's best-known play, which appeared in Edinburgh, Scotland, in August of 1966. Initially, it was considered as an amateur production. Later on, subsequent professional productions in New York and London in 1967 made him an international sensation. Now, after more than three decades and a number of major plays, he is considered as one of the most important playwrights in the latter half of the 20th century.

Needless to say that Tom Stoppard has been influenced by many writers but his borrowings are fused with his unique experiments and experiences. The two characters Rosencrantz and Guildenstern in Stoppard's play *Rosencrantz and Guildenstern are Dead*, their bewilderment and anxiety, their metaphysical speculation, the games in which they indulge resemble Vladimir's and Estragon's activities in *Waiting for Godot*. Guil (Guildenstern), like Vladimir, is intellectual and often gives to metaphysical speculations. Ros (Rosencrantz) is more like Estragon, more practical and placid than Guil, always likely to follow than to lead. As he pathetically puts it, "I can't think of anything original, I'm only good in support". Despite the difference there is a great bond between the two.

Ros and Guil of Stoppard's play are bound by Shakespeare's script. What makes the play look different is Stoppard's technique offering his fresh approach to it. Like *Waiting for Godot*, Stoppard makes the use of music-hall-pattern, and like *The Caretaker*, he employs clown-like circus technique in this play *Rosencrantz and Guildenstern are Dead*. We also find the use of pause and deflation. It's a play with conflicting points of view that mixes seriousness with farce and is filled with all kinds of word-play. For instance:

Ros: Rhetoric! Game and match! (Pause). Where's it going to end?

Guil: That's the question.

Ros: It's all questions.

Guil: Do you think it *matters*?

Ros: Does it *matter* to you?

Guil: Why should it *matter*?

Ros: What does it *matter* why?

Guil (teasingly): Doesn't it "*matter*" why it *mater*?"

This is how the Shakespeare's script takes the shape of absurd drama in Stoppard's

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hands. The two minor characters (Ros and Guil) of the play *Hamlet* become protagonists in Stoppard's play. They are focused in this play and we look at the world from their point of view. Being unimportant and common, like us, we identify ourselves with them.

Stoppard has Beckett's poetical intensity and suggestiveness. The play begins with Ros and Guil betting on the toss of a coin, as the coins, contrary to any law of probability, keep on coming down "Heads". We can say that the inevitability of "Head" is a suggestion of their inevitable death.

Again, on Claudius's order, Ros and Guil have engaged Hamlet in conversation, trying to get the bottom of his odd behavior. The interview proves worse than useless; to their twenty-seven questions he answered only three, so that Ros ruefully says that "he murdered us". Because we know "Hamlet", we can sense and appreciate the dramatic irony and suggestion contained in these words.

In *Hamlet*, Hamlet is the protagonist, and Ros and Guil are minor characters. They are friends. Claudius plots against Hamlet and these two Ros and Guil seem to be involved with Claudius. In a way, they seem to be betraying Hamlet. When they are put to death we do not feel sorry for them.

In Stoppard's play, Ros and Guil seem to be innocent and uninvolved in any malicious design against Hamlet. Ros and Guil are summoned to Claudius's court but are not informed the reason. At Ellsinore they receive the instructions to learn the secret of Hamlet's discontent. So they suspect that they have not been told the whole truth. They feel that they are being unfairly kept in the dark. As Guil says: "What a fine persecution - to be kept intrigued without ever quite being enlightened". p (30). They wonder why they have been chosen for the assignment from the very beginning. Guil says: "And why us? - anybody would have done p (67). After his, Ros and Guil receive instructions from Claudius to take Hamlet to England (along with the letter). They have, still, no idea what to do when they get there. When they discover that the letter contains a request to the king of England to have Hamlet put to death, they are confused. They cannot understand whether they should inform Hamlet. After few metaphysical speculations they postpone to inform Hamlet. When Hamlet turns the able to them they are shocked. They cannot understand what has gone wrong. Just before Ros's farewell line, he cries "We've done nothing wrong! We didn't harm anyone. Did we?" When such innocent people are put to death we feel sympathy for them. Their death moves us in this play, whereas in *Hamlet* it does not.

When we talk about their death some possibilities are worth mentioning. Despite their discovery what the letter contains, they do not inform Hamlet. Guil convinces Ros that they should not interfere and gives him several reasons why they should not.

Guil: "...It (death) might be...very nice. Certainly it is a release from the burden of life...Or to look at it another way - we are little men, we don't know the ins and outs of the matter, there are wheels within wheels; etc..." Guild's such rationalization is a typical of ordinary man's fear of action. The decision not to do or say anything here is what effectively gets them killed. Had they actually warned Hamlet, he would have had no reason to switch the letter as he did, consigning them o their deaths. It's one of the possibilities. We can say that they die because of their no fault. It was no their fate. They die not because of their inaction or the decision not to say

anything to Hamlet, they die just by chance!

Ros and Guil engage in conversation with the players on the meaning of death...To Guil death is simply non-being, a state of absence. Guil: "...Dying is not romantic, and death is not a game which will soon be over...Death is not anything...*It's the absence of presence*, nothing more...the endless time of never coming back...a gap you can't see, and when the wind blows through it, it makes no sound" p (90).

Guil's and Ros's deaths are a mere disappearance or a state of non-being. It is mere absence - during their lives they have achieved nothing, and understood nothing, their deaths are a mere vanishing into final anonymity and oblivion. They merely vacate the void they have been occupying.

Life is full of coincident and uncertainties and therefore life is complex. Sometimes we find no satisfactory answers to any of the mysterious that surrounds us. In order to penetrate them we often rely upon assumptions. This is what Ros and Guil do. The play begins with Ros and Guil betting on certainties. Actually they are summoned to Claudius's court at Ellsinore. But the whole situation becomes odd for them. So they go on tossing the coins. As a result, ninety-two coins spun consecutively have come down "heads" ninety-two consecutive times. And coming down of "heads" again and again increases their anxiety and perplexity. As a result the whole situation seems to be awkward and absurd. They are perplexed and much confused. Such state of mind brings forgetfulness. Like Godot's characters, here, no one can remember anything. They feel boredom. There is no peace of mind. Ros expresses his mental condition - "Newer a moment's peace! In and out, on and off, they're coming at us from all sides". So they wish to have a peace of mind.

They have a sense of freedom. The unicorn story is woven around it. Ros and Guil hope for a world in which unicorn actually exist, miracle can happen - and they can be free of the apparently inexorable laws that restrict them. As we know, unicorn is only a myth, it is illusion and it has nothing to do with reality. So the total freedom is not possible. Ros thinks that they will be free. To Ros's joyful anticipation of freedom in England once their mission is completed. Guil tersely replies, "I don't know it's the same sky" p (69). He sees sameness everywhere. Guil comes to realize that freedom is unattainable anywhere.

Ros and Guil have no identity of their own. They have no choice of their own. They are so common that they are often mistaken for each other. Throughout the play they are drifted away. They are lost souls. They do not have a sense of direction. Ros says: "I want to go home (moves). Which way did we come in? I've lost my sense of direction". So they feel that they are moving aimlessly, having no direction. Their life seems to be meaningless. As Guil feels that they "move idly towards eternity, without possibility of reprieve or hope of explanation". They are hopeless and helpless. And the entire life seems to be futile to them without having explanation of it. So Guil hopes that he may have a mystic experience which would give meaning to his life - just as Godot's coming would save Vladimir and Estragon from the shabbiness and, meaninglessness of their existence. They are disappointed just, again, as Vladimir and Estragon were disappointed by Godot's not coming. So finally they disappear leaving no significant marks behind them. Throughout their lives they were nothing and finally they disappear in nothingness and nobody notices them.

In this way, the disappearance of Ros and Guil gives raise to feelings of sorrow at the insignificance of men and his confusion and perplexity in a world which offer no clear-cut clues to any design or purpose.

References

Tom Stoppard, *Rosencrantz and Guildenstern are Dead*, (Faber Limited 24 Russell Square, London WCI, 1967). All page references are to Latimer Trend & Co. Ltd, Whitstable, reprinted in May 1968.

For Dawn, I'd Miss

Kay Salady*

The break of dawn has split the sky
 As purple clouds hang up so high
 To shroud remains of my stark night
 As I await the morning light
 When was the time I last saw sun
 Come greet my eastern horizon
 For in my bleakest solitude
 I'd always seen her rays as rude
 I've shunned the pain of her white light
 And sought my solace in the night
 For a cloak of darkness held me tender
 And in its silence I'd surrender
 Giving up the birds that sing
 The bees that hum and bells that ring
 For peaceful hours of quiet bliss
 I paid a price for dawn I'd miss